

**How to design and implement virtual reality-based learning activities:
an operational framework**

PROF.SSA ANGELA D'ANGELO

Module 1.
Introduction to virtual reality:
Oculus Quest headset

AR, VR or MR? INTRODUCTION

IMAGINATION IS
MORE IMPORTANT
THAN
KNOWLEDGE

```
<p> Albert Einstein </p>
```


MATRIX (1999)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hyshVa0-ceg>

«What is real? How do you define real? If you are talking about what you can feel, what you can smell, what you can taste and see, then real is simply electrical signals interpreted by your brain.»

Our perception corresponds to an attempt by the brain to interpret reality. The brain adds, subtracts, reorganizes, and encodes sensory information in order to interact with the external world.

Morpheus (Matrix, 1999)

What do you see?

And now?

Stereogram: how does it work?

A stereogram, stereoscopic image, or stereoscopic photograph is a flat, two-dimensional image designed to produce an illusion of depth.

Anything located at distances different from the point on which the gaze converges is processed by the brain as two distinct images, perceived respectively by the right and left eye. These minimal differences are processed by the visual centers of the brain to extract information about depth and the spatial position of the observed object (stereopsis).

This type of perception is referred to as stereoscopic vision, also known as binocular vision.

Virtual Reality: How Does It Act on the Brain?

The brain receives information from our sensory organs and transmits it to the brain as sensations. The brain then interprets this information (perception) from the five senses, enabling us to understand what is happening in the environment.

The interaction between sensation and perception creates our experience of reality. The subjective feeling of being somewhere is called presence.

But how does virtual reality actually achieve presence? How does it “trick” our brain?

How does VR “trick” our brain?

Visione stereoscopica: Un visore VR emula il funzionamento dei nostri occhi. La sensazione di presenza è data anche dal fatto che il visore isola dal mondo esterno e che i movimenti della nostra testa sono tracciati lungo gli assi X, Y e Z.

Latenza: se c'è troppa latenza, quindi velocità di risposta, tra i nostri movimenti reali e quelli riflessi nella realtà virtuale il cervello non può essere ingannato. La latenza non deve superare i 20 millisecondi.

Altri sensi: in particolare udito e tatto. Alcuni headset hanno un sistema ad audio spazializzato (posizionamento del suono in un ambiente 3D). Anche il tatto è importante: in commercio esistono guanti per la VR e tute VR.

Augumented Reality ≠
VIRTUAL reality ≠
Mixed Reality

Let's clarify...

Definition of AR and VR?

AR: Augmented Reality.

It refers to an “augmented” version of reality, created through the use of technology, which adds digital information by overlaying it onto the real environment. To achieve this, augmented reality relies on the use of a smartphone (or a tablet), on which an AR application can be installed.

VR: Virtual Reality.

Si intende una tecnologia capace di trasportarci in una realtà diversa da quella che stiamo vivendo. Questo avviene grazie a dei visori che, una volta indossati, sono capaci di isolare dal mondo e teletrasportare altrove. Quello che vediamo e sentiamo è rimpiazzato con qualcosa generato al computer, e con il quale possiamo interagire

AUGUMENTED REALITY

Pokemon GO...

MIXED REALITY

HOLENS MICROSOFT

<https://www.microsoft.com/it-it/hololens>

Mixed reality

Il termine Mixed Reality è stato introdotto in una carta del 1994 di Paul Milgram e Fumio Kishino, "A Taxonomy of Mixed reality Visual Display".

La realtà mista è una serie di esperienze immersive, che connettono e fondono il mondo fisico e quello digitale nelle applicazioni di realtà aumentata e realtà virtuale, uno spazio creativo che esiste tra gli estremi del mondo fisico e di quello digitale. Le esperienze vanno dalla sovrapposizione del contenuto virtuale agli oggetti del mondo fisico, ad esperienze completamente immersive in cui l'utente non ha alcun input dal mondo reale, come nella realtà virtuale.

AND METaverse?

Il termine è stato coniato da Neal Stephenson nel suo romanzo di fantascienza "Snow Crash" del 1992, in cui descrive un futuro in cui le persone vivono e lavorano in un mondo virtuale.

Il metaverso è un concetto che descrive un universo virtuale condiviso, che è costituito da molti mondi virtuali interconnessi e in cui gli utenti possono interagire in modo immersivo.

and **MULTIVERSE?**

Multiverso è il termine che alcuni fisici teorici usano per descrivere l'idea che al di là dell'universo osservabile (il nostro spaziotempo) possano esistere anche altri universi (dimensioni parallele).

Esistono vari scenari possibili: dalle regioni dello spazio in piani diversi rispetto al nostro universo, fino a distinti universi a bolla che emergono continuamente.

Virtual Reality

VR 3D or 360° Video?

In “true” 3D virtual reality, the environment is entirely (or partially) computer-generated.

There is a high level of user interaction (when supported).

In 360-degree images or videos, it is only possible to follow head movements and look around in the three directions.

There is little or no user interaction.

DOF: Degrees of freedom

DOF: Degrees of freedom

3DOF is typical of 360-degree videos, in which it is only possible to follow head movements and look around in the three directions. As a result, it is not possible to move forward or backward, bend down, or get closer to an object.

Why is this the case? What the user sees is the point of view of a camera that captured the scene from a fixed position. Consequently, interactivity is extremely limited, generally restricted to actions such as changing videos or environments and interacting with 2D elements placed within the scene (such as buttons, informational panels, and similar elements).

DOF: Degrees of freedom

6DOF, by contrast, characterizes 3D VR experiences, in which full immersion can be achieved. Users have complete freedom of movement thanks to the precise correspondence between movements in physical space and those in the virtual environment.

As a result, interaction becomes highly natural, allowing users to move freely, approach objects, grasp them, and interact with them.

Guide to Oculus Quest

First of all...

- The headsets must be charged and...
- The controller batteries must be charged
- The headset must be connected to Wi-Fi (headsets are excluded from Tutela)
- Adjusting the visual settings
- Defining boundaries
- Stationary mode (2 m diameter)
- Room-scale mode (requires much more space)
- Mirroring (requires a Meta account)
- Pass-through

29% 90% 90% • mer 5 feb 2025

Impostazioni

Wi-Fi
Illadbox-109268

Pass-through
SI

Mirroring
SI

Bluetooth
0 dispositivi

Confini
No

Microfono

Reimposta la vista

Display notturno

Non disturbare

Segnala un problema

Move

Modalità viaggio

13:38

Microfono

Reimposta la vista

Display notturno

Non disturbare

Segnala un problema

Move

Modalità viaggio

App Store

App

Contatti

Foto

Video

Browser

App Store

App

Contatti

Foto

Video

Browser

App Store

App

Contatti

Foto

Video

Browser

01

02

03

oculus.com - Per uscire dalla modalità a schermo intero, premere **ESC**

Cerca nelle impostazioni

Sistema Display, Comandi vocali, Accensione	Spazio fisico Confini, pass-through, configurazion...	Wi-Fi Iliadbox-109268	Personalizzazione Ambiente virtuale
Memoria Disponibile: 225 GB di 256 GB	App Autorizzazioni dell'app	Notifiche Non disturbare	Profil Aggiungi profili, gestisci la condivis...
Dispositivi Bluetooth, Tastiera, Mouse, Gamepad	Tracking dei movimenti Tracking delle mani	Accessibilità Correzione del colore, dimensioni del...	Privacy e sicurezza Pubblico e visibilità, connessioni soc...
Sicurezza Codice di accesso di sblocco per il vi...	Funzioni sperimentali Funzioni in fase di sviluppo	Meta Centro gestione account Gestisci le tue funzioni collegate e le...	Aiuto FAQ, tutorial e note sulla versione

11:39 [Wi-Fi] [Batteria] [Notifiche] [App Store] [Gmail] [App] [Meta] [Oculus] [Profil] [Impostazioni] [App Store]

Let's try...

Contents - VR

- APP META
- foto/video 360
- Tour virtuale
- Foto 360 AI
- Gioco 3D
- ...

Resources - VR

(free)

- YOUTUBE: video 360
- 360cities: video 360
- 360cities: gigapixel gallery
- 360cities: guided tour
- Google Art & Culture
- Google Art Voyager
- APP Meta

YouTube VR

<https://www.youtube.com/@360/featured>

Realtà virtuale

@360 · 3,42 Mln di iscritti

Learn more at <https://vr.youtube.com> ...altro

Iscriviti

Home **Playlist**

Playlist create

Ordina per

Music Collection 8
Visualizza la playlist completa

Recently Popular Collection 20
Visualizza la playlist completa

Travel Collection 8
Visualizza la playlist completa

Recently Popular Collection 19
Visualizza la playlist completa

Thrillseekers Collection 8
Visualizza la playlist completa

Explore Space in VR
Visualizza la playlist completa

Recently Popular Collection 18
Visualizza la playlist completa

Gaming Collection 7
Visualizza la playlist completa

Recently Popular Collection 17
Visualizza la playlist completa

Recently Popular Collection 16
Visualizza la playlist completa

Music Collection 7
Visualizza la playlist completa

Recently Popular Collection 15
Visualizza la playlist completa

YouTube

360 History
di SteveBamburyVR
Playlist · 109 video · 51.955 visualizzazioni

Riproduci tutto

I video non disponibili sono nascosti

-

Civil War: A Letter from the Trenches (360 Video)
American Heroes Channel · 1,3 Mln di visualizzazioni · 8 anni fa
-

Remembering Pearl Harbor VR: Experience History | 360 Video | TIME
TIME · 65.006 visualizzazioni · 8 anni fa
-

Battle Road: The American Revolution in 360/VR
CNERD · 199.140 visualizzazioni · 8 anni fa
-

360° Battle of Waterloo | National Geographic
National Geographic · 1,6 Mln di visualizzazioni · 7 anni fa
-

Atlantis Found: 360 VIDEO - Official First Look | History
HISTORY · 83.318 visualizzazioni · 9 anni fa
-

360° Viking Battle | National Geographic
National Geographic · 698.280 visualizzazioni · 7 anni fa

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLtZ/rcj9igDkXlcnWEw-lesQy7b4JMgBP>

YouTube VR

<https://www.youtube.com/@gigoistudios>

Gigoia Studios
@gigoistudios · 4000 iscritti · 135 video
Gigoia Studios creates Fine Art Games, Contemporary Art in Virtual Reality and ambient ...altro
gigoistudios.com e 5 altri link
Iscritto

Home Video Shorts Playlist

SURREALISTa Persistence of Memory VR - A fantasy over Salvador Dali
Gigoia Studios · 5035 visualizzazioni · 4 anni fa
DO YOU DREAM WALKING INSIDE A PAINTING IN VIRTUAL REALITY? Transpose yourself inside a SURREALIST world inspired by Salvador Dali! Explore a fantastic landscape filled with dreamy figures,...

Per te

- SURREALISTa Persistence of Memory 360**
15.920 visualizzazioni · 3 anni fa
360°
- POINTILLISTA SEURAT VR 360 | Version 2**
1650 visualizzazioni · 1 anno fa
360°
- STIJL Dream VR - IMMERSIVE PAINTING GAME**
2346 visualizzazioni · 4 anni fa
360°
- STRUCTUS VR 360 - Virtual Art In**
610 visualizzazioni · 2 anni fa
360°

360city.net

360 cities

Search...

EXPLORE

LEARN

SIGN UP/SIGN IN

Indonesia // Asia // The World

Open Map

360 Baja and Cyclo Glodok Jakarta

360° VIDEO GALLERY

GIGAPIXEL GALLERY

CURATED TOURS

WORLD MAP

360° STEREOSCOPIC

EDITORS' PICKS More >

SAVE DISCOUNT IMAGE PACKAGES

Barcelona Streets And Parks

Flight over snowy forest in North Europe

FOR TEACHERS

Slava Ukraini

Monastery Exteriors From Tibet To Spain

JANUARY STAR TOP VIRTUAL TOURS

Lavatories: Co Artistic, Spect Historical

schools.360cities.net

Search...

[World Map](#) [Guided Tours](#) [Help](#)

[Feedback](#)

Welcome back!

You now have access to over 350,000 high-resolution, fully-spherical 360° panoramas from around the world that you can integrate into your class blogs, LMS, and other websites that you use in your educational activities.

Just enter a word or search term into the [search box](#) or search by location on our [World Map](#). Both are in the header at the top of this and every page.

Share panoramas with your students by clicking on the share icon in the top right corner of the panoramas.

Create and share [Guided Tours](#) featuring 360° panoramas from our unique collection.

schools.360cities.net

Ancient Egypt: A POWERFUL CIVILIZATION

by 360schools

Over a period of 3,500 years, the ancient Egyptians built their civilization through the Nile river.

Google Art & Culture

Google Arts & Culture

[Home page](#)

[Esplora](#)

[Gioca](#)

[Qui vicino](#)

[Preferiti](#)

Scegli la tua avventura in 3D

Non è la solita visita al museo

Gallerie d'arte

Musei di storia

Mostre di design

Mostre naturalistiche

Immergiti nelle gallerie d'arte

Google Art & Culture

<https://artsandculture.google.com/project/expeditions>

Google Earth Voyager

<https://www.google.com/earth/about/gallery/>

Labster

<https://www.labster.com/simulations>

Content Catalog ▾

Disciplines ▾

Why Labster ▾

Resources ▾

About Us ▾

Get Pricing

Get Started

Courses

Clear all

- High School Chemistry
- Evolution
- Ecology
- Food Science and Nutrition
- AP Chemistry

Absorption In the Small and Large Intestines: Journey from the stomach to the bloodstream

In this simulation, you will step into the Anatomy and Physiology lab to discover how essential your intestine...

22 Min

Health Sciences

Biology

Higher Education

FREE TRIAL FOR TEACHER: 30 days

APP Meta

<https://www.meta.com/it-it/experiences/view/777073612853145/>

Meta Quest ▾ Ray-Ban Meta ▾ App e giochi ▾

Informazioni su Meta Assistenza ▾

Cerca

Home Giochi App Mondi Quest+ Lista dei desideri

Meta Quest ▾

Cerca mondi, app e altro ancora

Risparmia 50 € su Meta Quest 3S (256 GB). Acc

Meta Meta Quest ▾ Ray-Ban Meta ▾ App e giochi ▾

Home Giochi App Mondi Quest+ Lista dei desideri

Filtra (2)

Apprendimento ×

Esplorazione ×

Fly

★ 4,5 (748) • App • Esplorazione • Apprendimento
9,99 €

Jurassic World 2024

★ 3,6 (79) • App • Media • Apprendimento
Scarica

Human Anatomy

★ 3,8 (87) • App
Scarica
Early Access

Realità mista

Realità mista

Filtri

Ordina ▾

Genere ▲

- Acquisti
- App Hub
- Apprendimento
- Collegamento con il computer
- Community
- Creatività
- Esplorazione

Azzera i filtri

Examples:

Mission: ISS

TriptoVR: Travel The World, Explore

Space Explorers

Alcohol and Your Brain - A Rollercoaster Ride Through Your

Brain - NIAAA/NIH

Ecosphere

Electrical VR Training

...

Only english!

Web Resources

High definitions works of art

- **Getty Museum**

(<https://search.getty.edu/gateway/search?q=&cat=source&r=%22GRI+Digital+Collections%22&sources=%22GRI%20Digital%20Collections%22&highlights=%22Open%20Content%20Images%22&rows=10&start=a&dir=s&dsp=0&img=0&pg=1>)

- **The British Library**

- **Rijksmuseum**

- **The Met**

- **National Gallery of London**

MODULE 2

Virtual tours

360cities
Thingling

https://schools.360cities.net/

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL <https://schools.360cities.net> in the address bar. The browser's tab bar shows several open tabs, including 'PON Making', 'TUTOR', 'esp32', 'CLIL', 'ED.CIVICA', 'PNRR VR', 'PNRR AI', 'A040', and 'Atlante Italian Teach...'. The website's header features the '360 schools' logo on the left, a search bar with the placeholder text 'Search...', and navigation links for 'World Map', 'Guided Tours', and 'Help' in the center. On the right side of the header, there are 'Log In' and 'Sign Up' buttons. The main content area is dominated by a large blue banner with an underwater scene. The banner contains the text: 'Bring hundreds of thousands of incredible 360° panoramas to your students. Google Classrooms compatible'. Below this text is a prominent green button that says 'Sign up for a FREE account'. In the bottom left corner of the banner, there is a small attribution: 'Richard Chesher / 360Cities.net'.

https://schools.360cities.net/

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `schools.360cities.net/welcome-back`. The browser's address bar and tabs are visible at the top. The website header includes the '360 schools' logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'World Map', 'Guided Tours', and 'Help'. On the right side of the header, there are links for 'Feedback', a shopping cart icon, and a user profile icon.

Welcome back!

- You now have access to over 350,000 high-resolution, fully-spherical 360° panoramas from around the world that you can integrate into your class blogs, LMS, and other websites that you use in your educational activities.
- Just enter a word or search term into the [search box](#) or search by location on our [World Map](#). Both are in the header at the top of this and every page.
- Share panoramas with your students by clicking on the share icon in the top right corner of the panoramas.

https://schools.360cities.net/

https://schools.360cities.net/

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `schools.360cities.net/help/guided-tours/create-your-own`. The page features the 360schools logo, a search bar, and navigation links for World Map, Guided Tours, and Help. A featured video for Elena Martínez Bocos is displayed, with a 'Guarda su YouTube' button. The main content area contains instructions for creating a guided tour, a green 'Create your own Guided Tours' button, and a numbered list starting with '1. Begin by creating the Cover Slide for your Guided Tour. The Cover Slide is the introduction to the Guided Tour that you are about to create. It can include a title, a subtitle, and a panorama that serves as the background. Click "Save" to begin creating content for your Guided Tour.' Below the text is a button labeled 'Create a Cover Slide'.

https://schools.360cities.net/account/guided_tours

The screenshot displays the 'My Guided Tours' page on the website schools.360cities.net. The browser's address bar shows the URL. The page header includes the '360 schools' logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'World Map', 'Guided Tours', and 'Help'. A 'Feedback' link and a user profile icon are also present. The main content area features a heading 'My Guided Tours' and a green 'Create new Guided Tour' button. Below this, a descriptive paragraph explains that users can create and share up to three guided tours at once, with a 'Learn more' link. A table lists the user's current guided tours, each with its title and associated 'Share', 'Edit', and 'Delete' actions.

Title	Share	Edit	Delete
Esploriamo Parigi	Share	Edit	Delete
Il disastro di Chernobyl	Share	Edit	Delete
itinerario	Share	Edit	Delete

ADD NEW SLIDE

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `schools.360cities.net/account/guided_tours/9116`. The browser's address bar and tabs are visible. The page content includes a search bar, navigation links like "World Map", "Guided Tours", and "Help", and a main heading "Edit 'I luohi italiani della Grande Guer...". A modal dialog box titled "Add new slide" is open, displaying a list of slide types: "Panorama", "Text", and "Quiz". The "Panorama" option is selected. The dialog box has "Add" and "Cancel" buttons at the bottom right.

TEXT

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `schools.360cities.net/account/guided_tours/9116/guided_tour_slides/51674/edit`. The browser's address bar and tabs are visible at the top. Below the browser, the 360schools website header is shown, including a search bar and navigation links like "World Map", "Guided Tours", and "Help". The main content area features a title field with the text "Edit 'I luohi italiani della Grande Guerra' (Sli..." and "Save" and "Cancel" buttons. Below the title is a "Content" section with a rich text editor toolbar and a text area containing a paragraph about World War I.

schools.360cities.net/account/guided_tours/9116/guided_tour_slides/51674/edit

PON Making TUTOR esp32 CLIL ED.CIVICA PNRR VR PNRR AI A040 Atlante Italian Teach...

360schools Search... World Map Guided Tours Help Feedback

Edit "I luohi italiani della Grande Guerra" (Sli... Save Cancel

Title

Content

Sans Serif Normal B I U S List Bulleted List Numbered List Indent Decrease Indent Increase Text Color Background Color Quote Code X₂ X² Link

La Prima guerra mondiale, che inizia il 28 luglio 1914 con la dichiarazione di guerra dell'Impero austro-ungarico al Regno di Serbia, rappresenta il più imponente conflitto armato mai combattuto fino a quel momento. Le maggiori potenze mondiali, e le rispettive colonie, sono schierate in due blocchi contrapposti: da una parte gli Imperi centrali (Germania, Impero austro-ungarico e Impero ottomano), dall'altra l'Intesa (Francia, Gran Bretagna e Impero russo). Il 24 maggio 1915 anche l'Italia entra in guerra a fianco dell'Intesa e le sue truppe si muovono verso il confine con l'Austria-Ungheria: si crea così un fronte che si estende per 600 chilometri dall'Ortles all'Adriatico, collocato per due terzi nell'estremo nord-est del Friuli, tra Italia, Austria e Slovenia.

PANORAMA

Select a panorama

Enter 360schools panorama URL or a search phrase.

Tre Cime di Lavaredo

Search

or

Upload your own 360° panorama as a JPEG file. [Learn more](#)

Upload your own 360° panorama

Tre Cime di Lavaredo

Drone sunrise above the Drei Zin...

Drei Zinnen Hütte

Tre Cime Di Lavaredo

Tre Cime Di Lavaredo

Rifugio Locatelli - Tre Cime di ...

Dawn at Tre Cime di Lavaredo

Tre Cime di Lavaredo

Street View Download

Se l'immagine desiderata non è disponibile, è possibile crearla tramite l'APP "Street Views Download": <https://svd360.com/#downloads>

The screenshot shows the 'Street View Download 360' application interface. It features a green header bar with the title and window controls. A left sidebar contains navigation options: 'Panorama Download' (selected), 'Area Download', '360° Panorama Viewer', 'Settings', and 'About'. The main content area includes a file path input field set to 'C:\Users\user\Desktop\test-vr\cupola.jpg', radio buttons for 'Single panorama' (selected) and 'Multiple panoramas', a 'Panorama ID or URL' input field, a 'Resolution' dropdown menu set to '3328x1664', and a green 'Download Panorama' button. Below these fields, a 'Panorama Download' section provides a three-step instruction list.

Street View Download 360

- Panorama Download
- Area Download
- 360° Panorama Viewer
- Settings
- About

Path to save the file
C:\Users\user\Desktop\test-vr\cupola.jpg

Single panorama Multiple panoramas

Panorama ID or URL

Resolution
3328x1664

Download Panorama

Panorama Download

- Find the Google Maps and copy the URL.
- Paste the Path to save the file.
- Choose the image Download.

QUIZ

Edit "I luohi italiani della Grande Guerra" (Sli...

Title

Question

Possible answers

 Correct Correct

360cities

- 3 free virtual tours
- Ability to share via link (including with users who do not have an account)
- Ability to download content (paid feature)

Thinglink

60 free days for teachers
60 euros per year – full license

The screenshot shows the Thinglink pricing page with two tabs: 'K-12' (selected) and 'Formazione superiore'. Below the tabs are three pricing cards:

- Essential:** Inizia con la creazione di contenuti interattivi con l'accesso completo alla suite di prodotti ThingLink. Aggiungi in un unico account fino a 10 insegnanti e 200 studenti come creatori. A partire da **€1,000 / anno** fatturato annualmente. [REQUEST QUOTE](#)
- Enhanced:** Scatena la creatività degli studenti nella tua scuola, aggiungi fino a 25 insegnanti e 500 studenti come creatori in un unico account organizzativo. **Custom Pricing**. [REQUEST QUOTE](#)
- District:** Semplifica la creazione di progetti interattivi, tour VR e AR con accesso illimitato a ThingLink. Collega facilmente le statistiche di accesso e apprendimento con il tuo Sistema di Gestione della Formazione (LMS). **Custom Pricing**. [REQUEST QUOTE](#)

Thinglink

The image shows a web browser window with a sign-up form on the left and a Google account connection overlay in the center. The sign-up form includes fields for "Email" and "Password", a "CREATE ACCOUNT" button, and social media icons for Microsoft, Google, Apple, and Facebook. Below the form, it says "Already have an account? Log in" and "By signing up you agree to the Terms of Service".

The Google overlay, titled "Accedi con Google", shows the user's profile as "angela.dangelo@istitutotecnicoarconipilla.edu.it". It asks to "Seleziona gli ambiti a cui può accedere l'app ThingLink" and lists permissions with checkboxes:

- Seleziona tutto
- Visualizzare gli elenchi delle classi di Google Classroom. Scopri di più
- Visualizzare le classi di Google Classroom. Scopri di più

At the bottom of the overlay, it says "Poiché stai utilizzando Accedi con Google,".

The background of the browser window shows logos for Coca-Cola, Time Inc., Smithsonian, Stanford University, and New York, along with the text "10M+ content creators and some of the world's top companies and education institutions".

Thinglink: AI access (Copilot)

AI-Assisted Creation Flow (beta) Request

The next generation of ThingLink is here! Please fill out the form below to request access to ThingLink's new AI-assisted creation flow.

First Name*

Last Name*

Email*

Thinglink: examples

<https://www.thinglink.com/blog/five-examples-of-interactive-content/>

Thingling: contents creation

The screenshot displays the ThingLink web application interface. At the top, a dark banner contains the text: "Il periodo di prova di 60 giorni è terminato. Esegui l'upgrade alla nostra licenza Teacher per continuare a utilizzare ThingLink." followed by an "Aggiornamento" button. The main navigation sidebar on the left includes "Home", "Media", "Scenari", "Cestino", and "Comprimi". The central modal window, titled "Che tipo di contenuto interattivo desideri creare?", offers six options: "Immagine", "Immagine a 360°", "modello 3D", "Video", "Video a 360°", and "Contenuti misti". The background interface also shows a search bar, a "Crea" button, and a grid of content thumbnails, including one labeled "download (1) Vincent_van_...". A "Assistenza" button is visible in the bottom right corner.

Thinglink - image

<https://www.thinglink.com/view/scene/1415275080698560514>

Libertas

The statue is a figure of Libertas, a robed Roman liberty goddess. She holds a torch above her head with her right hand, and in her left hand carries a tabula ansata inscribed JULY IV MDCCLXXVI (July 4, 1776 in Roman numerals), the date of the U.S. Declaration of Independence.

Thinglink - image

Thinglink - scenari

thinglink Organizzazione Pagina di destinazione

Aggiornamento della licenza per insegnanti Usa il codice d'invito

Home **Generatore di scenari** versione 1.0 versione 2.0

Media

Scenari

Cestino

Comprimi

Scenario Builder

Generatore di scenari ThingLink

Gli scenari sono la soluzione di creazione di scenari di nuova generazione per l'apprendimento e lo sviluppo. È il modo più semplice e veloce per creare esperienze di apprendimento personalizzate con scenari non lineari e simulazioni virtuali da ambienti reali. Guarda il video per saperne di più.

[Scopri di più](#) [Crea scenario](#)

Benvenuto in Scenarios!

Thinglink

- 60 free days
- Classroom integration

Kuula

The screenshot shows a user dashboard for Kuula. On the left is a profile card for user 'ku61802' with a blue profile picture and an 'EDIT PROFILE' button. The main content area is titled 'Welcome to Kuula!' and includes a welcome message, a 'Upload your first tour' button, an 'Explore Featured Posts' button, and a 'Tutorials' section with buttons for 'Virtual Tour Tutorial', 'Custom Branding Tutorial', and 'All support articles'. Below this is a 'Kuula PRO' section with an 'Upgrade to PRO' button. On the right is a 'What's new?' section featuring a news item about 'Kuula launches Google Street View publishing' with a 'MORE NEWS' button, and an 'Articles and tutorials' section with 'Getting Started' and 'Virtual Tour Tutorial' links, and an 'ALL TUTORIALS' button.

MODULE 3

Dynamic Contents

Cospace EDU
Spatial

<https://www.cospaces.io/edu/>

<https://www.cospaces.io/edu/>

The screenshot shows the 'Piano di licenza' (License Plan) page in the Cospaces.io educator interface. The page has a purple header with the 'insegnante' logo and navigation icons. A left sidebar contains menu items: Galleria, Collezioni (marked 'PRO'), Classi, Progetti, and Archivia. The main content area is titled 'Piano di licenza' and has sub-tabs for 'Abbonamenti', 'Utenti', 'Classi', and 'Integrazioni'. Under 'Il tuo piano', a 'BASIC' plan is shown as the 'Piano attuale'. It includes '30 posti' and 'Nessun componente aggiuntivo', and is 'Valido fino al: Illimitato'. An orange 'Piano di aggiornamento' button is visible. At the bottom left, a status bar shows 'Posti occupati: 1/30' and a bottom navigation bar with 'Piano di aggiornamento' and 'Piano di licenza' (highlighted).

Galleria

CO SPACES EDU

Ricerca

...

...

...

Galleria

Classi

CoSpaces

Archivia

Galleria

STEM e Programmazione

Mostra tutto >

Marble maze game
CoSpacesTeam

Mystery of the lost cat
CoSpacesTeam

Prison Escape room
CoSpacesTeam

Atomic Parkour
sji0405

Still Water S.p.A.C. - P...
domysan91

Phishing test
domysan91

Scienze sociali

Mostra tutto >

Erasmus+ project - Me...
molinaayuso

Where in the world is ?
nathalie80

Reserva Animal World
TopVR_A

Roman House VR
CoSpacesTeam

Topdown Multiplayer ...
SmartLearnStudio

Parkour medieval
dthomas80Ambass

Lingue e letteratura

Mostra tutto >

Posti occupati: 1/30

Utenti

Passa alla versione Pro

Piano di licenza

ES: <https://edu.delightex.com/CHG-GEP>

MERGE CUBE: Delightex APP

COSPACES EDU MERGE CUBE

The MERGE Cube is a holographic cube for augmented reality made of semi-rigid black and silver rubber, featuring multiple symbols on each face. By rotating the cube in the hand, the 3D object displayed on the screen rotates accordingly.

MERGE CUBE

Many compatible apps

APP object viewer
APP Galactic explorer
APP 3D Museum Viewer
Paint 3D
Qlone

Creazione

The screenshot displays the CoSpaces Edu web interface. A modal window titled "Scegli una scena" (Choose a scene) is open, showing a grid of scene options. The modal has a question mark icon in the top left and a close button in the top right. The scene options are:

- Ambiente 3D (3D Environment)
- Immagine a 360° (360° Image)
- UNISCI Cubo (UNISCI Cube)
- Tour
- Empty scene
- Parkour game
- Multi diorama
- Large gallery
- Escape room temp...
- Roller coaster tem...
- Three scenes marked "PRO" (Premium)

At the bottom of the modal, there is a message: "Questo posto sembra vuoto. Riempilo con la tua creatività e crea un CoSpace." (This place seems empty. Fill it with your creativity and create a CoSpace.)

The background interface shows the CoSpaces logo, navigation tabs (Galleria, Classi, CoSpaces, Archivi), and a sidebar with options like "Posti occupati: 1/30", "Utenti", "Passa alla versione Pro", and "Piano di licenza".

Creation: ambient

Progetto - Scena 1

Pagina iniziale Annulla Ripristina Griglia Aiuto Condividi Codice Riproduci

Libreria Caricamento Ambiente

Ambiente Effetti **PRO** Filtri Immagine di sfondo Suono di sottofondo

Modifica

The interface shows a 3D scene of a snowy town square at night. The square is paved with a grid pattern and is surrounded by several buildings with snow-covered roofs and lit-up windows. Street lamps are visible along the edges of the square. The interface includes a top navigation bar with icons for home, undo, redo, grid, help, share, code, and play. A bottom toolbar contains icons for library, upload, environment, effects (PRO), filters, background image, and background sound. A 'Modifica' button is also present.

Skybox Blockade Labs

<https://skybox.blockade labs.com/>

360° image based on AI

Creation: library

Creation: upload

SPATIAL

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Pricing

Monthly

Annually

Save 20%!

Free

\$0

Per Space Per Month

- ✓ Basic content limit (100 MB)
- ✓ 10 participants
- ✓ Basic templates
- ✓ Branded w/ Spatial logo + ads
- ✓ 15 min daily screen share limit
- ✓ No analytics
- ✓ Basic Discord support

Get Started

Pro

\$8

Per Space Per Month

Everything in Free plus

- ✓ Standard content limit (500 MB)
- ✓ 50 participants
- ✓ Premium templates
- ✓ Unlimited screen sharing
- ✓ Standard analytics
- ✓ Access to Discord Channel

Upgrade to Pro

Business

\$80

Per Space Per Month

Everything in Pro plus

- ✓ Enhanced content limit (1000 MB)
- ✓ 1000 participants
- ✓ Auto full screen w/ no Spatial logo + ads
- ✓ Connect to External APIs
- ✓ Prioritized Support

Upgrade to Business

Enterprise

Custom

Per Space Per Month

Everything in Business plus

- ✓ Custom content limit
- ✓ Custom participant capacity
- ✓ Custom master service agreement
- ✓ Custom security incl. SSO, security audit, & private hosting
- ✓ Connect to External APIs
- ✓ Custom analytics
- ✓ Private Slack support

Learn More

The end

Questions?

Prof.ssa Angela D'Angelo

ITST MARCONI
CAMPOBASSO